

DESIGN OF SOLAR POWERED UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLE WITH PERPETUAL FLIGHT FOR SURVEILLANCE OF LONG-DISTANCE GAS PIPELINES

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ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Article History:

Accepted on 26 April

2022

Published on 25 July 2022

Keywords

Unmanned Aerial Vehicle, Conceptual Design, Solar Energy, Requirement Space Exploration, Design Space Exploration, Morphological Decomposition Matrix, UAV Design Analyses

The conceptual design of solar powered unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) with perpetual flight for surveillance of long-distance gas pipelines is very much needed. The requirement of this surveillance platform has been conceived due to terrorist attacks on gas pipelines in Baluchistan. Non-consumable and regenerative nature of the fuel used in solar powered UAV makes it an eternal plane under 24/7 energy balance. Such UAV operates as a terrestrial satellite, monitoring pipelines and transmitting real time imagery to control console. The requirement space was explored to select right specification matrix for the mission profile. The 24/7 flight endurance at 15,000 ft altitude during winter solstice is the key design constraint in addition to weight and power consumption of surveillance payload. Concept space was reconnoitered through Morphological Decomposition Matrix to select tail boom arrangement with non-retractable landing gears having multiple tractor electric propulsion units. Initial sizing is done to finalize Aspect Ratio and Wing span of baseline configuration. Detailed aerodynamic, propulsion, structural, stability, performance and cost analyses of this configuration are carried out to demonstrate conformance of all design requirements.

1. INTRODUCTION

The mission of electric powered unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) is primarily constrained by low flight endurance [1]. However, the endurance of these UAVs can be increased by utilizing solar energy,

ultimately achieving virtually sustained flight for telecommunication and surveillance missions. Out of 93 solar powered aircraft built till date, only few have demonstrated flight endurance of 24 hours [2]. Nevertheless, High Altitude Long Endurance (HALE) Solar Powered

UAVs have potential for surveillance and telecommunication applications. Financial effects of design, development and operation of satellite vis-à-vis HALE UAV also approve active research in field of UAV. Furthermore, recent improvements in the efficiency of Lithium Sulphide (LiS) batteries, photo voltaic solar cells and brushless DC motors are promising [3]. Yet, a successful endeavor to harness solar energy is essential for virtually eternal flight. The potential outcomes of solar powered UAV invites exploration in aircraft design and solar propulsion systems [4]. This study presents the conceptual design of high-altitude UAV with perpetual flight to carry out the surveillance of long-distance gas pipelines in Pakistan. The presented design meets all the mission requirements within technology constraints.

2. BACKGROUND

In 1974, Sunrise I made first solar powered flight [5]. Its photovoltaic cells were installed on the top surface of wing. It weighed 27.5 lbs with 32 ft wing span. In 1980, manned solar powered aircraft Gossamer Penguin made its maiden flight. It weighed 68 lb. without pilot and had a wing span of 71 ft [6].

In 1981, US Company AeroVironment began the development of HALSOL (High-Altitude Solar Energy) UAV. This UAV led to the development of solar powered UAV weighing 486 lbs called Pathfinder [7]. It had a wing span of 98 ft and could produce 8,000 watts (W) from solar cells. In 1997, Pathfinder flew at record altitude of 71,530 ft. Later, Pathfinder was modified to develop Pathfinder Plus which flew at altitude of 80 kft. The wing span was

increased to 121 ft along with installation of more efficient solar panels. The third UAV of the series was Centurion weighing 1300 lbs with a wing span of 206 ft. The fourth and last UAV of this series was Helios. It had a wing span of 247 ft with a weight of 2000 lbs. In 2001, Helios flew at an altitude of 96,500 ft. However, Helios disintegrated over Pacific Ocean during a test flight in June, 2003 [8].

In 2004, solar powered UAV Solang flew continuously for 48 hours [8]. Solang had 4 meters wingspan, 12.6 kg weight and power consumption of 65 watts (W). Solang is an impressive feat because it flew for 24 hours with solar power available during day time while remaining airborne. Solar Eagle (Vulture II) was a proposed HALE UAV developed by Boeing Phantom Works. However, this project was later cancelled in 2012.

ARCAspace® developed two solar powered medium sized UAV called Airstrato Pioneer and Airstrato Explorer, having 12 hrs and 20 hrs endurance respectively [9]. Both these UAVs can carry onboard 45 kg payload of surveillance and scientific equipment. Airstrato Pioneer carried out its maiden flight on 28 Feb, 2014.

MARRAL is a series of two solar powered UAV developed by Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Kanpur [10]. Marral-1 is low altitude UAV with 11 hrs endurance while Marral-2 is medium altitude UAV with 18 hours endurance. Several successful test flights have been carried out starting with maiden flight on 1st Feb, 2016. The latest capitalization of solar energy is marked by the design and development of Zephyr series HALE solar powered UAV

by British company QinetiQ. 03 out of 04 Zephyr UAVs are in service. Zephyr 8 is the largest UAV of the series with a wing span of 92 ft which can carry payload of 5 kg with an endurance of 26 days.

The review of design and development history of solar powered [7] UAV reveals that few UAV have achieved 24 hours endurance only during favourable sunny weather without any power consumption of onboard surveillance capabilities. Solar powered UAV with 24/7 flight endurance will be a terrestrial satellite. Non-consumable and regenerative nature of the fuel used in this solar powered UAV makes it an eternal plane [11]. Such UAV can be used for maritime surveillance and communication capabilities.

3. AIM OF RESEARCH

The aim of this research is to present conceptual design of solar powered UAV with perpetual flight endurance which can perform 24/7 surveillance of gas pipelines in Pakistan. Detailed aerodynamic, weight, structural, performance, stability and cost analyses have been presented which substantiate conformance of UAV with design requirements.

4. CONCEPTUAL DESIGN OF SOLAR POWERED UAV

4.1 Design Requirements

A recent history [12] of attacks on gas pipelines shows that most of attacks have occurred in Sui area [13]. There are 2 air strips in this area i.e., Jacobabad and Sui. UAV must be capable to take off and land from these airstrips. After takeoff, it must climb to safe altitude of 15,000 ft and cruise to the loiter area within a range of 65 miles.

UAV must have required surveillance equipment to monitor the ground activities in loiter area, data link to transmit the live imagery to ground console and flight control system. The weight and power consumption of this electronic equipment are 2 important design requirements [9]. Average payload and power consumption of COTS (Commercial of the shelf) payload is 55 lbs. and 225 watts respectively. UAV must be able to fly for 24/7 on winter solstice (i.e., 21st December) by utilizing available solar energy. UAV must harness solar energy during day time to fly and charge its onboard batteries. These onboard batteries then supply power for night flight. If UAV is able to fly on shortest day of the year i.e. 21st December for 24 hours, then it can fly around the whole year without landing [14]. This is termed as 24-hour energy balance because the solar energy available during the day must be equal to or greater than the energy used for day flight and charge batteries for overnight flight [15]. Non-consumable and regenerative nature of solar energy being utilized to power UAV implies that a solar powered UAV with 24 hours endurance on shortest day of year can fly round the year.

4.2 Conceptual Design Methodology

Conceptual design methodology presented by Noth and Siegwart [16] is suitable for initial sizing of solar powered High altitude lone endurance (HALE) UAV. It is based on 24 hours energy balance where by solar panels installed on UAV convert solar energy into electric energy during the day time. During day, available electric energy not only powers UAV but also charge onboard batteries. These batteries supply power to UAV during night when solar energy is not available.

Iterative design cycle used for initial sizing of solar powered UAV is given in Fig. . Empirical aerodynamic data for high performance sailplanes including Lift Coefficient ($C_L=0.8$), Drag coefficient ($C_D=0.015$) and Oswald Efficiency ($e=0.9$) is utilized for initial sizing. Span (b) and Aspect Ratio (AR) are 2 design variables used to optimize the configuration of UAV [17]. In addition to these two design variables, this methodology has 2 further groups of parameters.

1. The first group of parameters is circumscribed by existing technology. These parameters when optimized for a particular application are considered as constant. Mean data of solar powered UAVs has been utilized and is given in Table 4. Invariably, increase in efficiency of electrical and mechanical components result in the decrease in total mass of UAV.
2. The second group of parameters is assumed constant for the design mission profile of UAV and is based on design requirements.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Design Methodology for Solar Powered UAV

Table 4: Efficiency of Electrical and Mechanical Components

Parameter	Value
Battery Charge/ Discharge ($\eta_{charge/discharge}$)	0.98
Efficiency Max Power Point Tracker (η_{mppt})	0.97
Efficiency Step-down Converter (η_{BEC})	0.7
Efficiency Control Servos ($\eta_{control}$)	0.95
Efficiency Solar Cells (η_{cells})	0.25

3. High altitude and long endurance solar powered UAV is similar in design and performance to sail planes [18]. Raymer Design Methodology is applicable for Sail plane design [19]. Therefore, detailed aerodynamic, structural, weight, stability, performance and cost analyses have been carried out as delineated by Raymer.

4.3 Mass Estimation Model

Total mass of UAV is the summation of masses of individual components. Therefore, a good mass model for each component is required to estimate the mass (m) of UAV [20]. Design constraints govern the mass and power consumption of payload. In addition, following heuristics

are used to estimate the mass of aircraft components [21].

1. Mass and power consumption of flight control system is estimated as 1% and 1.2% of mass (m_{control}) and power consumption (P_{control}) of UAV respectively.

2. The mass of battery is directly proportional to the energy required and inversely proportional to its energy density. The amount of electric energy stored per unit mass of the battery is defined as Battery energy density (K_{battery}). For LiS batteries utilized for the current application, K_{battery} is taken as 350 J/kg.

3. The mass of solar panel is directly proportional to the area covered by solar panels A_{solar} . Presently, commercially available solar panel has mass to area ratio 0.54 kg/m^2 which is sum of mass density of solar cell (k_{cell}) and encapsulation (k_{encaps}). For sustained 24 hours flight endurance, the total electric energy consumed each day is equal to the total electric energy obtained from the sun. This energy balance given in Eq. (1) provides the area of solar panels:

$$P_{\text{electric tot}} \left[T_{\text{day}} + \frac{T_{\text{night}}}{\eta_{\text{charg}} \eta_{\text{discharg}}} \right] = \frac{2I_{\text{max}} T_{\text{day}} K_{\text{sol margin}}}{\pi} \quad (1)$$

4. Maximum Power Point Tracker (*MPPT*) is an electronic device installed in solar power system which adjusts the voltage to provide maximum power. Eq. (2) gives the mass of MPPT (m_{mppt}) which is directly proportional to available solar power ($P_{\text{sol max}}$)

$$m_{\text{mppt}} = k_{\text{mppt}} P_{\text{sol max}} =$$

$$k_{\text{mppt}} I_{\text{max}} \eta_{\text{charg}} \eta_{\text{mppt}} A_{\text{sol}} \quad (2)$$

Where k_{mppt} is mass to power ratio for MPPT, typically approximated as 0.00047 Kg/W

5. The mass of the propulsion group depends upon the propulsive power required and can be estimated by Eq. (3)

$$m_{\text{prop}} = K_{\text{prop}} P_{\text{prop}} = 0.0045 P_{\text{prop}} \quad (3)$$

6. Statistical data for high efficiency sail planes has been utilized to develop heuristics for the structural weight of HALE solar powered UAV. The structural weight of the UAV is given in Eq. (4) as a function of span (b) and aspect ratio (AR).

$$m_{\text{struct}} = b^{X1} k_{\text{struct}} AR^{X2} = b^{1.5551} * (12.31) * AR^{-0.311} \quad (4)$$

7. Total mass of UAV (m_{tot}) is sum of control system, payload, solar cells, battery, MPPT, airframe and propulsion system and is given by Eq. (5).

$$m_{\text{tot}} = m_{\text{cntrl}} + m_{\text{payload}} + m_{\text{cell}} + m_{\text{batt}} + m_{\text{mppt}} + m_{\text{struct}} + m_{\text{prop}} \quad (5)$$

4.4 Morphological Decomposition Matrix

In order to select best configuration for solar powered UAV, various alternates [22] are explored using qualitative reasoning through morphological decomposition matrix. This matrix of alternatives is given in

propulsion units in a tractor configuration is selected. Selected configuration has non-

Table 5. Tail boom design with multiple

retractable landing gears to perform conventional takeoff and landing. Flexible solar panels are selected for installation on the wing. These solar panels will charge onboard high density LiS batteries.

4.5 Radiance Model

Radiance model is developed to incorporate the solar propulsion system into the design cycle by calculating the available solar energy [23]. Solar power varies with

geographic location, calendar date and time of the day. 24 hours endurance on 21st December is a design constraint. Radiance model of complete year for 29.52° latitude is given Fig.. Available solar energy in loiter area is equal to area under the radiance curve. Maximum Irradiance (I_{max}) and available solar energy is 896 W/m² and 20.68 MJ/m² respectively.

Table 5: Morphological Decomposition Matrix

Variable	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3	Selected
Configuration	Conventional	Boom tail	Flying wing	Boom tail
Solar Panel Location	Wing and tail	Wing	Tracker	Wing
PV Type	Rigid	Flexible	--	Flexible
Energy source	Solar Cells	Storage batteries	Hybrid	Hybrid
Battery	Li Ion	LiPo	LiS	LiS
Landing gears	Retractable	Non retractable	N/A	Non retractable
Take off	Dolly launch	Rail launch	Conventional	Conventional
Landing	Net Arresting	Belly landing		
Propeller	Twin	Four	Multiple	Four
Propeller location	Pusher	Tractor	--	Tractor
Propeller Pitch	Fixed	Variable	--	Variable pitch

Fig.2: Irradiance Available Throughout Year

4.6 Aircraft Sizing

Based upon the design requirements, initial sizing of UAV is carried out [24]. Design of Experiments (DOE) has been carried out to explain the variation in weight of solar powered UAV due to changes in AR and span. Total 230 UAV with AR from 8 to 32 have been converged on mass and 24-hour energy balance. Fig. and Fig. relate weight and total power consumption of converged UAVs as function of AR and span. Total power consumption of UAV is sum of mechanical power consumption, electrical

power consumption and energy losses including friction and heat losses. UAV with minimum weight has been selected as base line configuration. In order to improve aerodynamic performance, low Reynolds No airfoil AH94-145 with taper ratio 0.3 at mid span is selected. The selected (optimized) configuration has AR 16 with 78.8 ft span, 441 lbs weight, and reference wing area S_{ref} 388.4 ft². Loiter speed of the UAV is 24.34 knots with a total power consumption of 1283.5 ft. lb. /sec. Fig 3 represent the geometric view of optimized configuration.

Fig.3: Weight of UAV as function of Span and Aspect Ratio

Fig.4: Power Consumption of UAV

4.7 Aerodynamic Analysis

Vortex panel method is used for aerodynamic analysis of wing, vertical and horizontal tail [25]. This method provides zero lift drag coefficient (C_{Do}) and coefficient of lift induced drag (C_{Li}) for lifting surfaces. Component build up method is used to incorporate aerodynamic effects of landing gears, fuselage, tail booms etc. In conjunction with vortex panel method, component build up method is used to determine drag polar for UAV during various flight phases. Fig. presents drag polar of UAV during takeoff, cruise and landing.

Fig.6: Drag Polar During Various Phases of Flight

Fig. 5: Draft Model of UAV

4.8 Propulsion Analysis

During conceptual design phase, characteristics of propulsion system for UAV are based on historical trend [9]. In Helios and Heliplat [6], multiple brushless direct current DC motors power 2-blade variable pitch propellers through intermediary gear boxes. The same scheme has been employed through 4 Commercial off the shelf (COTS) brushless electric DC motors (Make Himax 2200-watt Ea.) to provide propulsion power (P). Diameter of each propeller (d) is estimated to be 2.38 ft using Eq. (6)

$$d(ft) = 1.83 \sqrt[4]{P(hp)} \tag{6}$$

Efficiencies [3] of high performance propeller ($\eta_{prop}=0.9$), gear box ($\eta_{gear\ box}=0.9$) and electric motors ($\eta_{motor}=0.95$) are used for calculation of available thrust (T) within flight envelop using Eq. (7). Fig 7 provides variation of available thrust (T) as function of airspeed (v).

$$P = \eta_{prop} \eta_{gear\ box} \eta_{motor} T \cdot v \tag{7}$$

Fig.7: Variation of Thrust with Indicated Air Speed

4.9 Structural Analysis

Lift is primarily generated by wings of solar powered UAV. Resultant aerodynamic forces generate shear loads and bending moments on the wing. Fig 8 presents the span wise distribution of lift force at 3° AOA at various airspeeds. The shear force at each span station is equal to sum of lift loads outboard of that span station i.e., the integral of distributed lift load.

Fig.8: Span-wise Lift Distribution on Wing

Bending moment equals summation of lift loads times the distance from the span station i.e., integral of distributed lift load

with respect to the distance from the span station. Fig 9 gives performance of aircraft in form of maximum load factor achieved at different velocities at 3 different altitudes within the flight envelop.

Fig.9: V-N Diagram of UAV with Gust Effect

4.10 Weight Analysis

Heuristics from Noth model [20] have been used to calculate weight of solar powered UAV. Therefore, a comparison of this UAV with solar powered UAVs and high-performance sailplanes has carried out on Great Flight Diagram in Fig.. Designed UAV falls between McCormick Boundaries defined by Eq. 8 below;

$$\frac{W}{S} = 85.5 \left(W^{\frac{1}{3}} - 9.9 \right) \ \& \ \frac{W}{S} = 44.8 \left(W^{\frac{1}{3}} - 9.9 \right)$$

Total weight of UAV is 441 lbs with reference wing area S_{ref} 388.4 ft². Comparison of weight and wing loading of this UAV with other solar powered UAV and sailplanes is presented in Table 6 which shows that designed UAV follows average tendency due to use of heuristics-based model.

Fig.10: Weight and Wing Loading of UAV on Great Flight Diagram

Table 6: Comparison of Wing Loading with Solar Powered UAVs

UAV	Total Weight (lb)	S_{ref} (ft ²)	W/S (lb/ft ²)
Sunrazor	2050	2008	1.02
Centurion	1900	1596	1.19
Path Finder	485	263	1.83
Solair	440	236	1.86
Solar	337	234	1.43
Designed UAV	441	388	1.13

4.11 Stability Analysis

Using Raymer methodology [19], static stability analysis of solar power UAV has been carried out. The subject methodology provides step by step procedure for calculation of interceding aerodynamic and stability coefficients. The results are reported to conclude that UAV has positive static longitudinal stability ($C_{L\alpha} = 5.45/rad$) with 9.9 % Static Margin (SM), positive directional stability ($C_{m\alpha} = -0.54/rad$) and positive lateral stability

($C_{n\beta} = 0.0715/rad$).

4.12 Performance Analysis

Mechanical Power required to overcome drag force (D) for sustained flight is given by Eq. 9 below;

$$P_R = D \cdot v = [C_D q S] v = [(C_{D0} + 0.02C_L^2) q S] v$$

By means of drag polar available from aerodynamic analysis, propulsive power required to overcome drag force for sustained flight at various altitudes within flight envelop has been plotted in Fig..

Radiance model provides solar power available for onboard conversion to mechanical power. This available mechanical power has been plotted as straight line on the graph for 21st December and 21st March. It is evident that mechanical power available from solar energy on 21st December is more than power required for 24 hours flight. Therefore, it validates that UAV is capable to perform 24 hours endurance throughout year on solar power only up to airspeed of 43 kts. Furthermore, total engine power available from 4 DC motors is sufficient to accelerate UAV up to speed of 100 kts. However, sustained operation at such speeds will limit flight endurance due to increased drag.

Fig.11: Available and Required Power for UAV

4.13 Cost Estimation

Rand Corporation DAPCA IV cost model [26] is used to estimate the cost of UAV during and after amortization period. This cost model is based on cost estimation relationships developed in 1986 for conventional metal aircraft. Raymer corrections [19] for inflation and composite structure of UAV have been introduced through Consumer price index (CPI) and fudge factors. Cost of UAV during and after the amortization period is given in Fig 12.

Fig. 12: Production Cost per UAV During and After Amortization Period

5 DISCUSSION ON RESULTS

In order to carry out the surveillance of gas pipelines, onboard reconnaissance equipment is required. Therefore, power consumption and weight of this equipment are the design constraints which have been incorporated in iterative design cycle. Radiance model is used to calculate maximum irradiance and available solar energy in worst case scenario i.e., 21st December. The conceptual design methodology for solar powered UAV is utilized for initial sizing of HALE platform. The 230 solar powered UAV have been converged on mass and energy balance to select a baseline configuration with minimum weight. Heuristics have been used to estimate mass of individual UAV components. Using morphological decomposition matrix, tail boom design with multiple propulsion units in a tractor arrangement is selected. The selected configuration has non-retractable landing gears to perform conventional takeoff and landing. Flexible solar panels are selected for installation on the wings. These solar panels not only provide energy for daytime flight but also charge onboard batteries. These batteries supply power to UAV during night when solar energy is not

available. This baseline configuration has been optimized with low Reynolds number Airfoil AH94-145 with taper ratio 0.3 at mid span. The solar powered UAV is capable to takeoff from landing strip at Sui or Jacobabad with on board reconnaissance equipment. It can climb to an altitude of 15,000 ft to a loiter area 62 nautical miles away and can perform 24/7 endurance flight in worst case scenario i.e., 21st December. On basis of DAPCA IV cost model, estimated cost for full scale production UAV is approx. 4.7 million PKR (USD 40,000)

6 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the detailed analysis performed on the solar powered UAV, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Conceptual design methodology for solar powered UAV has been exploited successfully to design solar powered HALE platform with 24/7 endurance.
2. The feasibility of solar powered surveillance UAV is established with existing efficiency constraints of solar cells, storage batteries and composite materials.
3. All design requirement for surveillance of long-distance gas pipes with solar powered UAV have been successfully met.
4. Non-consumable and regenerative nature of the fuel used in solar powered UAV makes it an eternal plane under 24/7 energy balance. Such UAV is a cost-effective terrestrial satellite, monitoring pipelines and transmitting real time imagery to control console.

The following recommendations are made in light of analysis presented in this study:

1. Numerical analysis and wind tunnel testing of model can be performed to validate preliminary results of the conceptual design and analyses of this UAV.
2. Development of scaled down technological demonstrator is recommended to establish proof of concept.
3. The effects of wind and thermals may be studied to reduce thrust requirements of the solar powered UAV.

7 REFERENCES

- [1]. Sai, L., Z. Wei, and W. Xueren. *Development Status and Key Technologies of Solar Powered Unmanned Air Vehicle*. in *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*. 2017. Hainan Province, China.: IOP Publishing.
- [2]. Morton, S., R. D'Sa, and N. Papanikolopoulos. *Solar Powered UAV: Design and Experiments*. in *IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. 2015. Prague, Czech Republic: IEEE.
- [3]. Rajendran, P. and H. Smith. *Review of Solar and Battery Power System Development for Solar-powered Electric Unmanned Aerial Vehicles*. in *Advanced Materials Research*. 2015. Prague: Trans Tech Publ.
- [4]. Hajian Maleki, M. *Conceptual Design Method for Solar powered Aircraft*. in *49th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting*. 2011. West Mount, USA: CRC.

- [5]. Kumar, G., S. Sepat, and S. Bansal, *Review Paper of Solar-powered UAV*. International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, 2015. **6**(2): p. 41-44.
- [6]. Baldock, N. and M. Mokhtarzadeh-Dehghan, *A study of Solar-powered, High-altitude Unmanned Aerial Vehicles*. Aircraft Engineering and Aerospace Technology, 2006. **13**(7): p. 2147-2149.
- [7]. Zhu, X., Z. Guo, and Z. Hou, *Solar-Powered Airplanes: A Historical Perspective and Future Challenges*. Progress in aerospace sciences, 2014. **71**(4): p. 36-53.
- [8]. Hoffborn, M., *A Historical Survey of Solar powered Airplanes and Evaluation of it's Potential Market*. 2009, AIAA: Atlanta, Georgia. p. 127-129.
- [9]. Alsahlani, A. and T. Rahulan, *Conceptual and Preliminary Design Approach of High Altitude, Long Endurance Solar-powered UAV*. CSE-PGSym, 2017. **4**(3): p. 241-243.
- [10]. Dwivedi, V.S., et al. *MARAAL: A Low Altitude Long Endurance Solar-powered UAV for Surveillance and Mapping Applications*. in *2018 23rd International Conference on Methods & Models in Automation & Robotics (MMAR)*. 2018. Bombay: IEEE.
- [11]. Lee, J.-S., et al. *Design of Virtual Flight System for Evaluation of Solar Powered UAV*. in *39th Annual Conference of IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*. 2013. Vienna, Austria: IEEE.
- [12]. Mubin, S. and G. Mubin, *Risk Analysis for Construction and Operation of Gas Pipeline Projects in Pakistan*. Pakistan Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences, 2016. **1**(1): p. 21-22.
- [13]. Garlick, J., *Deconstructing the China–Pakistan economic corridor: pipe dreams versus geopolitical realities*. Journal of Contemporary China, 2018. **27**(112): p. 519-523.
- [14]. Oettershagen, P., et al. *Perpetual Flight with a Small Solar-powered UAV: Flight Results, Performance Analysis and Model Validation*. in *2016 IEEE Aerospace Conference*. 2016. Montana, USA: IEEE.
- [15]. Lee, B., et al., *Active Power Management System for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Powered by Solar Cells*. IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems, 2014. **50**(4): p. 3167-3177.
- [16]. Noth, A., *Design of Solar Powered Airplanes for Continuous Flight*. 2008, ETH Zurich. p. 41-44.
- [17]. Van Nguyen, N., et al., *A Multidisciplinary Robust Optimisation Framework for UAV Conceptual Design*. The Aeronautical Journal, 2014. **118**(1200): p. 123-142.
- [18]. Shiau, J.-K. and D.-M. Ma, *Development of an Experimental Solar-powered Unmanned Aerial Vehicle*. Journal of Chinese Institute of Engineers, 2015. **38**(6): p. 701-713.
- [19]. Raymer, D., *Aircraft Design: a Conceptual Approach*. 4 ed. 2012, Reston, VA, USA: American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Inc. 141-148.

- [20]. North, A., R. Siegwart, and W. Engel, *Autonomous solar UAV for Sustainable Flights*, in *Advances in Unmanned Aerial Vehicles*. 2007, Springer: ETH Zurich. p. 377-405.
- [21]. Xian-Zhong, G., et al., *Parameters Determination for Concept Design of Solar-powered, High-altitude Long-endurance UAV*. *Aircraft Engineering and Aerospace Technology*, 2013. **12**(6): p. 214-218.
- [22]. Sadraey, M.H., *Aircraft design: A Systems Engineering Approach*. 2012, New Jersey, U.S.A: John Wiley & Sons.
- [23]. Rajendran, P., H. Smith, and M.H. bin Masral. *Modeling and Simulation of Solar Irradiance and Daylight Duration for a High-power-output Solar Module System*. in *Applied Mechanics and Materials*. 2014. Prague: Trans Tech Publ.
- [24]. Jashnani, S., et al., *Sizing and Preliminary Hardware Testing of Solar powered UAV*. *Egyptian Journal of Remote Sensing and Space Science*, 2013. **16**(2): p. 189-198.
- [25]. Panagiotou, P., et al., *Aerodynamic Design of a MALE UAV*. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 2016. **50**: p. 127-138.
- [26]. Scanlan, J., et al., *Cost Modelling for Aircraft Design Optimization*. *Journal of Engineering Design*, 2002. **13**(3): p. 261-269.